

BLESync: Wireless Synchronization Between Computers and Tap Tempo Effect Pedals

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ABSTRACT

Electric guitar players often rely on a disparate combination of pedals, whose effects are an essential aspect of the performance language. Many of these effects feature time-based parameters such as delay time or modulation frequency. In a performance incorporating computers and guitars, these parameters should ideally be synchronized with the song tempo as determined by software. While some modern effect pedals incorporate MIDI inputs that can be used for synchronization, a large amount of them require tempo to be "tapped" by stepping on an additional footswitch. In this demo, I present BLESync, a simple MIDI Bluetooth LE device that facilitates the synchronization between a computer and multiple tap tempo-based devices. A wireless connection allows better physical on-stage independence between the computer and the guitar performer.

1. INTRODUCTION

The electric guitar is an extremely versatile music instrument. The combination of elements in its sound chain (the instrument itself, the amplifier, effect units, etc.) give the performer access to an endless tonal palette. By definition, the most radical sound transformations are achieved with effect devices, most commonly implemented in a pedal form factor. Musicians mix and match units to customize their sound, becoming an defining aspect of their performance language [1][2].

Many popular effects depend on time-based parameters. Some examples are the time parameter in echo or delay pedals, and the low frequency oscillator (LFO) in modulation effects such as tremolo, flanger and phaser. By adjusting delay time and LFO frequencies it is possible—and most often desirable—to synchronize the effect to the current song tempo. While MIDI Clock [3] is a frequently used method for synchronizing digital instruments and effects, many effects pedals do not feature MIDI capabilities, hence tempo synchronization is done by means of a "tap tempo" footswitch. While this is a reasonable solution when performing with a band of human musicians,

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Figure 1. BLESync

accurate synchronization of an effects pedal with a digital system using tap tempo is difficult.

I introduce *BLESync* (Figure 1), a Bluetooth LE (BLE) MIDI device that allows wireless synchronization between a computer and tap tempo effect pedals. BLESync's output connects to effects pedals' tap tempo input and simulates tapping by means of a relay switch. Its internal tempo is updated whenever the tempo in the master computer changes, and three taps are sent to its output whenever the internal tempo is updated. The result is that the connected pedal stays synchronized with the master computer, while sparing the need of running additional cables across the stage.

2. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 Hardware

Wang et al. [3] evaluated the performance and compatibility of BLE MIDI and concluded that it has potential for replacing wired MIDI interfaces. With this in mind, I built BLESync around the Adafruit Feather 32u4 Bluefruit microcontroller [6], which features a Bluetooth radio compatible with BLE MIDI. This allows the microcontroller to be recognized by computers, mobiles and tablets as a wireless MIDI device. The Feather offers other advantages, including a built-in LiPO battery connector and charger and the possibility to connect a diversity of peripherals, called "FeatherWings". I used a FeatherWing OLED display to visualize the current parameters of the device, including current tempo, tempo signature of the delay, delay time (in milliseconds) and whether the tempo is set internally or externally, i.e., for switching between setting the tempo manually or from a computer via Bluetooth.

Figure 2. Block diagram

A rotary encoder with a built-in push button, connected to GPIO pins of the Feather, allows the following operations:

- Rotating the encoder manually adjusts tempo when not slaving to a computer.
- By briefly pushing the encoder, the tempo signature switches between different fractions of a beat (1/1, 1/4, 3/4). More values could easily be added with simple firmware code changes.
- If the encoder is pressed for more than 2 seconds, BLESync will switch between tempo sources, i.e. Bluetooth (*EXT*), manual (*INT*) or both (*I+E*).

Another GPIO pin from the Feather controls a relay whose output contacts are connected to a TS jack in the case of the device. A simple patch cable can be used to connect this jack to the tap tempo input of the pedal to be controlled. By opening and closing the relay in quick succession, a tap tempo action is simulated hence controlling the internal tempo of the pedal.

The device is enclosed in a custom-made, laser-cut methacrylate box.

2.2 Software

An Arduino/C++ sketch running on the Feather manages the Bluetooth connection, OLED screen, user input and relay control. The sketch requires several Adafruit’s libraries for Bluetooth LE, Bluetooth MIDI and OLED display.

Tempo encoding

MIDI clock is the preferred synchronization method for MIDI devices, thus it would be a natural choice for this project. However, MIDI clock is not part of the Bluetooth MIDI specification [3]. The alternative is to transmit tempo changes as a continuous controller (CC) values. As single CC value are limited to the 0-127 range, tempo can be encoded as a MSB and LSB combination using CC 16 and 48 (general purpose CC, as per MIDI specs [3]) to allow a wide range of tempos. The encoding is simple:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tempoMSB} &= \text{bpm} / 10 \\ \text{tempoLSB} &= \text{bpm} \% 10 \end{aligned}$$

Where Both `tempoMSB` and `tempoLSB` are integers, and ‘%’ is the modulo (division reminder) operator. Decoding at the receiving end is also very simple:

$$\text{bpm} = \text{tempoMSB} * 10 + \text{tempoLSB}$$

Figure 3. Interface showing current tempo, internally set (i.e. manual, using the encoder), with a signature of 1/2 beat. The period (e.g. delay time) is also shown in milliseconds.

Computer side

In this demo, I use Ableton Live running on MacOS as a master tempo source to control BLESync. As with any BLE MIDI device, a manual connection step is required to make the MIDI port active and available for MIDI software. On MacOS this is done with the Audio MIDI Setup utility. A Max for Live patch obtains the current song tempo from Ableton Live’s real time playback information (by means of the `[plugsync~]` object) and applies the encoding described earlier. The patch is inserted in a MIDI channel, whose output is set to be the BLESync MIDI port. The result is that, whenever Live’s tempo changes, the new value is transmitted wirelessly to BLESync and its internal BPM value is adjusted accordingly. Please note that, although I use a combination of Ableton Live and Max for the purpose of this demo, the tempo encoding can be implemented with any piece of software that supports MIDI CC messages.

The Arduino sketch and Max4Live patch are available for download at <https://github.com/jpcarrascal/BLESync>.

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3. REFERENCES

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